

XX-ASRNING 30-YILLARIDA OSIYO MAMLAKATLARI

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Annotatsiya. Butun Yaponiya diplomatiyasi turli hiyla-nayranglar bilan o'z maqsadlarini yashirishga harakat qilgan. Londonda yaponlar tashabbusi bilan Xitoyni qaytadan ta'sir doiralari bo'lish haqidagi muzokaralar boshlanadi. AQShga amerika-yapon do'stligini mustahkamlashni targ'ib qilish va antisovet holatini vujudga keltirish uchun bir guruh yapon jurnalistlari jo'natiladi. 1931-yil avgustida yapon monopoliyasi oligarxi Okura bir guruh amerika banklari rahbarlari va kongress liderlari bilan uchrashuvlar o'tkazadi. Uchrashuvda SSSRga qarshi birlashishni qat'iyat bilan ta'kidlaydi

Kalit so'zlar: Yaponiya, Koreya, diplomatiya, SSSR, Minami diviziyasi.

ASIAN COUNTRIES IN THE 30S OF THE 20TH CENTURY

Abstract. The entire Japanese diplomacy tried to hide its goals with various tricks. On the initiative of the Japanese, negotiations on the division of China into spheres of influence begin in London. A group of Japanese journalists is sent to the United States to promote the strengthening of American-Japanese friendship and create an anti-Soviet situation. In August 1931, Japanese monopoly oligarch Okura held meetings with a group of American bank executives and congressional leaders. At the meeting, he insists on uniting against the USSR

Key words: Japan, Korea, diplomacy, USSR, Minami division.

СТРАНЫ АЗИИ В 30-Е ГОДЫ 20 ВЕКА.

Аннотация. Вся японская дипломатия пыталась скрыть свои цели различными ухищрениями. По инициативе японцев в Лондоне начинаются переговоры о разделе Китая на сферы влияния. Группа японских журналистов направляется в США для содействия укреплению американо-японской дружбы и создания антисоветской обстановки. В августе 1931 года японский олигарх-монополист Окура провел встречи с группой руководителей американских банков и лидеров Конгресса. На встрече он настаивает на объединении против СССР.

Ключевые слова: Япония, Корея, дипломатия, СССР, дивизия Минами.

1929-1932-yillardagi dunyo iqtisodiy inqirozi Yaponiyada ichki ijtimoiy muammolar va AQSh, Angliya hamda boshqa yirik davlatlar bilan raqobatlarini kuchaytiradi. Qishloqlarda feodal qoldiqlarning ustunligi, turmush tarzining qoloqligi ichki savdoda cheklanganlikka olib keladi.

Iqtisodiy inqiroz natijasida Yaponiya eksporti 32%, import esa 30%ga pasayadi. Tashqi savdoning pasayishi Yaponiya iqtisodiga juda katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Narxlarning tushib ketishi natijasida noyob mahsulotlar narxining 60% ko'tarilishiga, yollanma ishchilarning ahvolini yomonlashishiga olib keladi. Yaponiyada ishsizlar va ish bilan ta'minlanmaganlar soni 3 mln kishiga yetadi¹.

¹ История дипломатии. Москва. 1959. С. 638.

Ular bu vaziyatdan fashistik davlatlar bilan munosabatlarni yaxshilash va tashqi ekspansiyani kuchaytirish orqali chiqib ketishni maqsad qiladilar. 1930-yil sentyabrda markaziy apparatdagi bir guruh zobitlar podpolkovnik Xisimoto “Gullagan olcha jamiyati”ni tuzadilar.

Yashirin tashkilotning dasturida Manchjuriya (shimoliy-sharqiy Xitoy) va Mongoliyani bosib olish ilgari surilgan edi².

Shimoliy-sharqiy Xitoy provinsiyalari va Mongoliya ancha vaqtdan buyon yaponlarni o‘ziga jalb etib kelardi. Manchjuriya hududi sanoat mahsulotlari uchun bozor va xom ashyo bazasi (ko‘mir, cho‘yan va boshqa mahsulotlar) hisoblanar, hududdagi chet el kapitalining asosiy qismi Yaponiya kapitalistlariga tegishli edi (taxminan 1,5 mlrd ien).

Ayni paytda, Xitoyda yaponlarning mamlakat ichkarisiga kirishiga qarshilik kuchayib boradi. Angliya va amerika sarmoyadorlari Yaponiyani Manchjuriyadan siqib chiqarish uchun Xuludao nomli Uzoq portni va shu bilan parallel ravishda YUMJD (janubiy Manchjuriya temir yo‘li)ni qurishni davom ettiradilar. Bu yaponlarning noroziligiga sabab bo‘ladi. Yaponlar Manchjuriyani bosib olishni o‘zlarining birinchi darajali vazifasi deb hisoblab, bu yerdagi chet el kapitalini siqib chiqarishni va kelajakda Xitoy hamda SSSRga qarshi platsdarmga aylantirishni maqsad qilgan edilar.

1931-yil 12-martga mo‘ljallangan isyon amalga oshmay qolsa-da, hukumat tarkibini o‘zgarishiga olib keladi. Bu hukumatga harbiy vazir etib, qo‘shindagi fashist guruhlari bilan mustahkam aloqada bo‘lgan general Minami tayinlanadi³.

1931-yil 4-avgust kuni instruktiv majlisida Minami diviziyasi shimoliy-sharqiy Xitoy va Mongoliyadagi masalasini harbiy yo‘l bilan hal etishga bag‘ishlangan yig‘ilishi o‘tkaziladi.

Generalning muammoni harbiy yo‘l bilan hal qilish haqidagi taklifi targ‘ibot vositasi sifatida qabul qilinadi. Harbiy-siyosiy doiralar bu inqirozdan faqat urush yo‘li bilan chiqish mumkinligini yoqlaydilar⁴.

Manchjuriyani “bolshevik ta’siri”dan qutqarish maqsadida antisovet targ‘iboti kuchaytiriladi. Dastlabki davrda g‘arb davlatlari yaponlarning bu yerdagi targ‘ibotlari faqatgina SSSRga qarshi qaratiladi va Xitoydagi mulklarga hech qanday daxl qilmaydi degan fikrda edilar.

Yapon diplomatlari ham o‘zlarining antisovet shiorlari Vashington, London va Parijda xaryixohlik bilan qarshi olinadi degan niyatda bo‘lganlar⁵.

Butun Yaponiya diplomatiyasi turli hiyla-nayranglar bilan o‘z maqsadlarini yashirishga harakat qilgan. Londonda yaponlar tashabbusi bilan Xitoyni qaytadan ta’sir doiralariga bo‘lish haqidagi muzokaralar boshlanadi. AQShga amerika-yapon do‘stligini mustahkamlashni targ‘ib qilish va antisovet holatini vujudga keltirish uchun bir guruh yapon jurnalistlari jo‘natiladi. 1931-yil avgustida yapon monopoliyasi oligarxi Okura bir guruh amerika banklari rahbarlari va kongress liderlari bilan uchrashuvlar o‘tkazadi. Uchrashuvda SSSRga qarshi birlashishni qat’iyat bilan ta’kidlaydi⁶.

² Молодяков В.Э. Эпоха борьбы: Сиратори Тосио (1887-1949): дипломат, политик, мыслитель. Москва. 2006. С. 45

³ Кошкин А. А. Предыстория заключения пакта Молотова-Мацуока//Вопросы истории. 1993.№ 6. С. 154.

⁴ История дипломатии. Москва. 1959. С. 639

⁵ Ўша асар. С. 640

⁶ История международных отношений. Основные этапы с древности до наших дней. Москва. Логос. 2007. С. 57

Yaponlarning antisovet kompaniyasi AQSh boshqaruv guruhlarini tomonidan xayrixohlik bilan qarshi olinadi. Amerika diplomatiyasi esa doimiy ravishda yapon-sovet munosabatlarini buzilishi uchun harakat qiladi va AQSh davlat kotibi Stimson 1931-yil bahorida bu haqda shunday degan edi: “Mamlakatlarimiz o‘rtasidagi abadiy va mustahkam do‘stligimiz abadiydir. Okean bizni ajratmaydi, aksincha, birlashtiradi”⁷.

1931-yil 17-sentyabrda yapon diplomati Debutsi AQSh davlat kotibi Stimson huzuriga oddiy vizit bilan boradi. Stimson va Debutsi masalani muhokama qiladilar va ikki davlat o‘rtasidagi munosabatlar oldindan ham hozirgidek do‘stona bo‘lganligini ta’kidlaydilar.

Shu kuni AQShning Yaponiyadagi elchisi Forbs tashqi ishlar vaziri Sidexara huzurida bo‘lib, u bilan Manchjuriya holati haqidagi masalani muhokama qiladi. Shimoliy Xitoydagi vaziyat soat sayin murakkablashib borayotgan edi. Davlat departamentida so‘zga chiqqan AQShning Xitoydagi elchisi Jeyson bu haqida ma’lumot beradi. 1931-yil mart oyidayoq amerika razvedkasi Yaponiyaning tez orada Manchjuriyaga bostirib kirishi haqidagi ma’lumot bilan tanish edi. Ammo amerika rahbarlarida Yaponiyaning Manchjuriyaga kirishiga to‘sqinlik qilish rejalari bo‘lmagan. Chunki, shimoliy-sharqiy Xitoydan boshlanib, mamlakat ichkarisigacha rejalashtirilgan KVJD (Xitoy harbiy temir yo‘li) Yaponiya va SSSR o‘rtasidagi to‘qnashuvni keltirib chiqarishi kerak edi⁸.

Yapon diplomatiyasi hujumga zo‘r berib yordamlasha boshladi. 1904-yili Rossiyaga qarshi urush boshlamasdan oldin Nankin hukumatini tartibga solish haqidagi muzokaralar boshlangan edi. Yapon elchisi olib borilayotgan muzokaralar shimoliy-sharqiy Xitoydagi butun bahsli masalalarni tartibga solishi mumkinligi haqida bayonot beradi.

Xitoydagi Chan Kayshi hukumatining SSSRning mamlakat ichkarisigacha kirib borish va bu yerda ta’siri kuchayishiga qarshi kurashi yapon diplomatiyasiga qo‘l kelar edi. Nankin va Shanyan hukumatlari 1929-yildagi Xabarvosk bayonida yuklatilgan majburiyatlarini bajarmayotgan edilar. Shimoliy-sharqiy provinsiyalarida oqgvardiyachilarning SSSR va Xitoy o‘rtasidagi qarama-qarshilikni kuchaytirayotgan faol harakatlari davom etayotgan edi.

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⁷ История дипломатии. Москва. 1959. С. 640

⁸ Латышев И.А. Внутренняя политика японского империализма накануне войны на Тихом океане. 1931-1941. Москва. Госполитиздат, 1955. С. 89.

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